

Gravity | Density

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1 PROGRAM NOTES

Gravity | Density is a work for cyber-hacked devices and Web Audio applications with thematic material drawn from humankind's fascination with the universe.

In *Gravity | Density*, we begin by manipulating fixed-audio sources through the performance of hacked CD players. The sonic results of this mangled audio is sampled and then distributed to the audience's mobile devices in both passive and interactive manners. Passive distributions allow us to create intricately-spatialized rhythmic interplay between the glitching CD players and the blanket of overlapping samples dispersed throughout the networked audience. Active distributions allow the audience to join in our performance; by sampling small portions of the audio, processing and looping these sounds and sending them back to the performers, we string this audio together and feed it into a cyber-controlled distortion pedal before sending it back to the audience for more manipulation. This results in overlapping cycles of control and audio generation between performer, audience, network, and machine.

Fig. 1. *Gravity | Density* in performance

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2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Gravity | Density is a work for cyber-hacked devices and Web Audio applications.

Our impetus was to develop systems that merge repurposed and hacked pieces of hardware into the networked world of web art. While the electronic sophistication of mobile devices and the flexibility of web applications allow artists to create immerse audiovisual environments without the use of traditional music hardware, we believe that digital artists should not cast aside the tools of the past, but rather make creative modifications so that they can be assimilated into this new digital, web-based artistic practice. Through these hybrid systems, we can both embrace the limitations and push the boundaries of any hardware we use for the purpose of creating collaborative sonic performances.

Fig. 2. *Gravity | Density* mobile UI

3 MEDIA LINKS

- Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DV7H69ak18w>
- Audio: gravity.emdm.io/gravWAC.mp3
- Further Documentation: gravity.emdm.io